

The Role Of Jordanian Television In Combating Terrorism From The Viewpoint Of Jordanian Journalists

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of Jordanian journalists. The study sample consisted of 150 journalists, who were selected by the intentional sampling method. The study used the method of the questionnaire to limit the phenomenon, to statistically analyze it, classify it, measure and draw conclusions from it. The study found that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists at a medium level. The study showed that all members of the study sample have close-level perceptions regarding the degree of Jordanian television's contribution to combating terrorism by gender. The study showed that all of the individuals I recruited have close-level perceptions regarding the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism, depending on the job.

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1. Introduction

Heavenly laws, charters, and humanitarian principles criminalize terrorism in all its forms and manifestations. Its manifestations have varied and its concept has expanded to include multiple crimes. Despite constant international efforts to combat it and eliminate its plans, this danger continued to threaten the security of individuals and societies (El-Desouki, 2016).

The world's interest in terrorism increased at the beginning of the twenty-first century, which is classified as the most dangerous scourge known to nations, although it has been stable in the consciousness of humanity since ancient times. Humanity has faced it since its emergence, as a result of the destructive effects it arranges on the lives of individuals and societies, and the spread of terrorism has been linked to the development and depth of current events in the global arena, so that the concept of terrorism has become relevant to every event, whether planned or otherwise, and the main general framework governing the movement of states and their various policies (Akakna, 2016).

Terrorism has become a source of fear, fear and anxiety, especially since it is not a conventional war, but rather appears in the form of multiple terrorist acts and in the form of unorganized guerrilla warfare, as happens in the Arab countries and elsewhere. The great powers were not far from his evils and plans, so that we find that the most important and dangerous is that countries are facing an unknown enemy, not knowing when, where, how it appears, why and who to direct its destructive strikes (Nawal, 2016)

Therefore, this research paper seeks to identify the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of Jordanian journalists, and the great role that the visual media plays at this stage in combating the phenomenon of terrorism.

The study problem and its questions:

The media has become a basic element in building societies, in terms of what the satellite channels broadcast in the spirit of the stereotype related to the events taking place in this world. And because the media is an effective and influential tool in society, it must be used to combat the phenomenon of terrorism that the Arab world and the world are witnessing during the current time. The visual media is one of the main pillars in the fight against terrorism, and from this standpoint, Jordanian television has an important role in promoting trends and ideas that combat the phenomenon of terrorism. Therefore, the problem of the study is confined to answering the following main question: What is the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism? The following sub-questions were divided into this question:

- 1- Are Jordanian journalists exposed to Jordanian TV?
- 2- What is the role of Jordanian TV in combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists?
- 3- What is the role of Jordanian TV in combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists, depending on the job change?

4- What is the role of Jordanian TV in combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists, according to the gender variable?

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of the study are crystallized as follows:

- 1- Learn about the role of Jordanian television in the fight against terrorism.
- 2- Knowing the extent of Jordanian journalists' exposure to Jordanian television.
- 3- Learn about the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists, according to the job change.
- 4- Learn about the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism among Jordanian journalists, according to the gender variable.

The importance of study:

The importance of this study stems from the following:

- 1- Explain the importance of the role of Jordanian television in the fight against terrorism
- 2- It may help those in charge of the local and Arab media in finding new media mechanisms to combat terrorism.
- 3- The possibility for academics and media professionals to benefit from its results in conducting research and studies in combating terrorism.
- 4- Other satellite channels in Jordan and abroad may benefit from the results of the study in improving their media performance in the face of terrorism.
- 5- The scarcity of researches and studies that dealt with the role of Jordanian television among Jordanian journalists
- 6- The importance of getting to know the role of Jordanian television in the fight against terrorism.

Variables of the study:

Independent variables:

- 1- Sex variable and has two levels: males and females.
- 2- Functional variable and has two levels: delegate and editor.

Dependent variables:

It is represented in the responses of the study sample members to the areas of the questionnaire represented in what Jordanian television is fighting terrorism.

Previous studies:

The research literature indicates the relatively scarcity of field studies related to the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism, despite the existence of numerous studies dealing with the issue of terrorism, and we will present the most prominent things related to the current study.

The study of Al-Shardaqa, Tahsin(2016) that entitled "The role of the media in combating the phenomenon of terrorism and extremism from al-Qaeda to the emergence of ISIS.". The study used the descriptive and analytical approach, aimed to identify the role of the media in combating the phenomenon of terrorism and extremism.

The study showed that the media play a high role in combating terrorism and extremism, according to the study sample represented by faculty members in Jordanian universities.

The study of Chefs, Othman (2016) entitled "The extent of the contribution of Al-Rai Newspaper in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of students of the Faculty of Information at the University of the Middle East." The study aimed to identify the extent of the contribution of Al-Rai newspaper in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of students of the Faculty of Media at the Middle East University. The study used the descriptive and analytical method, indicated that Al-Rai newspaper contributes to the fight against terrorism from the viewpoint of students of the Faculty of Mass Communication at the Middle East University at a medium level. The study found that all members of the study sample have similar level perceptions regarding the degree of Al-Rai newspaper's contribution to combating terrorism by gender.

The study of Nawal, Obaid(2016) that entitled "The Role of the Media in Combating the Phenomenon of Terrorism from the Viewpoint of the Journalists". The study aimed to identify the role of the media in confronting the phenomenon of terrorism from the viewpoint of the media.

The results of the study, which used the survey approach, confirmed that the media plays an important role in confronting the phenomenon of terrorism, according to the sample of the study, which was represented by the journalists at the Press House and the regional television station in the eastern Algerian capital Constantine.

The study of Al-Nawafleh, Makhled(2010) that entitled "The Jordanian public's attitudes towards terrorism issues broadcast by the Al-Jazeera and Al-Arabiya satellite news channels ... a field study." The study aimed to identify the trends of the Jordanian public regarding terrorism issues that are broadcast by Al-Jazeera and Al-Arabiya channels through their news programs and audio and video recordings. The study used the descriptive

approach, showed that the Jordanian public's attitudes toward terrorism issues broadcast by the two news channels Al-Jazeera and Al-Arabiya were moderate.

The study of Mansour, Tahseen(2007) entitled "The role of Jordanian television in shaping the attitudes of university youth towards terrorism issues." The study aimed to identify the role of Jordanian television in shaping the attitudes of university youth towards terrorism issues. The study used the descriptive and analytical method, where the questionnaire of the study was distributed among (371) individuals. And they were tested by a simple random method. The study revealed that there were no differences in evaluating the Jordanian television coverage of the terrorism issue due to the gender variable.

The study of Durham.(1998) entitled "New York Times press coverage of the crash of the Boeing 747 aircraft belonging to established airlines across the world in the late 800th in 1996." The study aimed to identify the New York Times press coverage of the crash of the Boeing 747 belonging to the established airlines across the world in Flight 800 in 1996. The study showed a decline in the newspaper's role in shaping the public's attitudes and knowledge, as the accident was the result of a terrorist act or a technical defect.

After reviewing the previous studies on the subject of the study, the following is evident:

First: Most of the previous studies agreed on the extent of the media's great potential to influence the masses

Second: No study - as far as the researcher knows - has investigated the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism. Since visual media has an important role in influencing the attitudes and convictions of society, this study came to examine the role of the media in combating terrorism.

Third: The present study is in agreement with the study of Al-Shardaqa (2016), the Chefs (2016), Al-Nawafleh (2010) and Mansour (2007) in the method used, which is the descriptive and analytical method.

Procedural concepts:

Some terms will be used in this study, which will be mentioned in it, and are considered among the main terms in it, namely:

Jordanian TV: In this study we mean the official Jordanian television.

Terrorism: It is the method or method that a party or an organized group tries to achieve its goals by using violence, force and cruelty and directs it against people, whether they are individuals, groups, or representatives of the authority who oppose their goals (Al-Haidari, 2015).

The Arab Convention on Combating Terrorism and Terrorist Crime defined it as: "Every act of violence or threat thereof, regardless of its motives or purposes, takes place in the implementation of an individual or collective criminal project, and aims to throw terror among people or terrify them by harming them or endangering their lives, freedom or security," Or damage to the environment or a public or private facility or property, or its occupation or seizure, or endanger a national resource (Al-Dulaimi, 2010)

Method and procedures:

After looking at the theoretical framework and previous studies, the researcher clarified the most important methods and means used to reach his goals in this study, which examines "the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism ... from the viewpoint of Jordanian journalists." In this regard, it specifies the procedures that the researcher followed to carry out the study and obtain the necessary data. The following is a detailed presentation of the most important methods and measures taken in this study:

Study methodology

This study is based on the use of a descriptive and analytical approach, as it monitored the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism from the point of view of Jordanian journalists, collected data about it, and then analyzed it with the aim of reaching specific results that contribute to explaining the phenomenon and answering the study questions through a questionnaire distributed to the study sample .

Study population and sample:

The original population of the study consisted of Jordanian journalists, the number of which was according to the statistics of the Jordanian Journalists Syndicate (1200) journalists, and the study sample was determined by the intentional method, reaching 512 percent of the study population, and the researcher was able to distribute the questionnaire to (150) journalists, and after retrieving the questionnaires, Done

Excluding (30) of them because they are not valid for the purposes of statistical analysis, so the final sample was represented by (120) questionnaires, which represent (100%) of the main sample, and the following is the demographic distribution of the study sample individuals shown in Table (1):

Table (1)
Distribution of the study sample according to demographic data

Variable	Frequencies	%
Sex		
Male	70	58.3
female	50	41.7

Total	120	100.0
Occupation		
editor	63	52.5
representative	57	47.5
Total	120	100.0

Study instrument "questionnaire":

The study tool consisted of the study questions and was composed of:

- The first section: demographic information, which consists of: gender and occupation..
- The second section: that measures the study questions related to the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism, which is represented in statements (1-16).

Validate the study instrument:

The questionnaire was presented to a number of arbitrators who have extensive experience in the field of media and terrorism, to verify the validity of its statements. Their opinions were taken, some statements were reformulated, and the required amendments were made, in a manner that accurately achieved a balance between the contents of the questionnaire in its statements, and they expressed their desire to interact with its statements, which confirms the validity of the tool.

Reliability of the study tool:

To calculate the reliability of the study tool, the researcher used the method of the internal consistency equation using the Cronbach alpha test, where the Cronbach alpha values for the study variables and for the resolution in general were higher than (60%), which is an acceptable ratio in research and studies, where the tool reliability coefficient reached (98.3).

Statistical treatment:

Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were used, using the statistical package (SPSS). The frequencies and percentages were extracted and the Cronbach alpha test was used. In order to answer the study questions, arithmetic means and standard deviations were used, and an Independent Sample T-test was used.

Correction key:

The results of the descriptive statistical analysis of the data were relied upon, which include the arithmetic means and standard deviations of all the independent study axes and the component statements for each axis. It has been taken into account that the Likert scale used in the study is as follows:

Degree of agreement				
Strongly agree	Agree	neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
5	4	3	2	1

Based on the foregoing, the values of the arithmetic averages reached by the study will be dealt with as follows: (3.68 - and above: high), (2.34-3.67: medium), (2.33 - or below: low). According to the following equation:

Highest value - the minimum value of answer alternatives divided by the number of levels, i.e.:

$(5 - 1) \div 4 = 1.33$, and this value is equal to the length of the class.

3 3

Thus, the low level of $1 + 1.33 = 2.33$

And the medium level is $2.34 + 1.33 = 3.67$

The high level is from 3.68 to 5.

Results:

The questions of the study:

This study seeks to answer the following question:

1- What is the role of Jordanian TV in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of Jordanian journalists?

Arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted to identify the responses of the study sample individuals about the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism from the journalists' point of view, and Table (2) illustrates this:

Table (2)

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the respondents of the study sample from the statements on "The role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism from the viewpoint of Jordanian journalists" arranged in descending order.

No	Statement	Mean	S.D	Rank	Level
3	I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism by broadcasting international news related to terrorism.	3.39	0.96	1	medium
2	I find that Jordan TV contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting regional news related to terrorism.	3.37	0.93	2	medium
7	I find that Jordan TV contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting terrorism-related comedies.	3.36	1.01	3	medium
10	I find that Jordan TV contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting youth programs that warn of the danger of terrorism.	3.36	0.97	3	medium
11	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn society of the danger of terrorism to Jordanian national security.	3.36	0.99	3	medium
1	I find that Jordan TV contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting local news related to terrorism.	3.35	0.92	6	medium
9	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting awareness programs that show the dangers of terrorism.	3.29	1.02	7	medium
4	I find that Jordan TV contributes to the fight against terrorism by broadcasting the media report on terrorism.	3.28	0.93	8	medium
6	I find that Jordan TV contributes to fighting terrorism by broadcasting press analyzes related to terrorism.	3.28	0.92	8	medium
14	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn of the danger of terrorism to national unity.	3.27	0.99	10	medium
13	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn society of the danger of terrorism to global security and stability.	3.26	0.92	11	medium
16	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that spread the values of moderation and moderation.	3.26	0.98	11	medium
5	I find that Jordan TV contributes to the fight against terrorism by conducting interviews with specialists in the field of terrorism.	3.23	0.96	13	medium
12	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn society of the danger of terrorism to Arab national security.	3.22	0.86	14	medium
8	I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism through its dramatic programs.	3.17	0.96	15	medium
15	I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn society of the danger of terrorism in dividing Arab countries.	3.17	0.92	15	medium
	Total mean	3.29	0.85		medium

It is clear from Table No. (2) that the arithmetic mean for (the role of Jordanian television in the fight against terrorism) ranged between (3.39 and 3.17), where the axis obtained an overall arithmetic medium(3.17),

which is of the medium level, and statement No. (3) The highest medium is (3.39), and with a standard deviation (0.96), which is of the medium level. The statement stated (I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism by broadcasting international news related to terrorism). And in second place came Statement No. (2), and the statement had a mean of (3.37) and a standard deviation (0.93), which is of the medium level, where the statement stated: (I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism by broadcasting regional news related to terrorism), And in third place came Statement No. (7) with an arithmetic mean(3.36) and a standard deviation (1.01), which is of the medium level. The statement stated: (I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism by broadcasting comedies related to terrorism). In the last place came Statement No. (15) With an arithmetic mean of (3.17) and a standard deviation (0.92), which shows of the medium level? The statement stipulated (I find that Jordanian television contributes to combating terrorism by broadcasting programs that warn society of the danger of terrorism in the division Arab countries), and in the penultimate rank, Statement No. (8) came with an arithmetic mean(3.17) and a standard deviation (0.96), which is of the medium level, as the statement stipulated (I find that Jordanian television contributes to the fight against terrorism through its dramatic programs).

This explains that Jordanian television plays a mediating role in combating terrorism from the point of view of Jordanian journalists, and these results are consistent to some extent with the results of the previous study (Al-Tahat, 2016) which confirmed that Al-Rai newspaper plays a mediating role in the fight against terrorism, and these results also agree to some extent with The results of the previous study (Al-Nawafleh, 2010), which showed that the Jordanian public’s perception of terrorism issues broadcast by Al-Jazeera and Al-Arabiya channels was moderate, while these results differed somewhat with the previous study (Al-Shardaqa, 2016), which confirmed that the media play a high role in the fight against terrorism and extremism. .

Results of the second question

Text of the question: To what extent are Jordanian journalists exposed to Jordanian television?

To answer the second question, the frequencies, percentages, and a graph were extracted to identify the extent of Jordanian journalists' exposure to Jordanian TV, and tables (3) illustrate this:

Table (3)

Frequencies and percentages to identify the extent of Jordanian journalists' exposure to Jordanian television

Journalists were exposed to Jordanian television	Frequencies	%
Very Much	29	24.2
Sometimes	64	53.3
Rarely	27	22.5
Total	120	100.0

Table (3) shows that (24.2%) of the study individuals are exposed to Jordanian TV a lot, and (53.3%) of the study individuals watch Jordanian TV occasionally, and (22.5%) of the study individuals rarely watch Jordanian television. This indicates that the percentage of journalists watching (exposure) to Jordanian television was of a medium level, and the following chart shows that:

Figure No. (1) shows the extent of journalists' exposure to Jordanian television

Results of the third question:

Question text: Are there statistically significant differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism due to gender?

The Independent Sample T-test was used to identify the differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism due to the gender variable, and Table (4) illustrates that:

Table (4)
Independent Sample T-test to identify the role of Jordanian television in the fight against terrorism due to gender

Source	Total Gender	Mean	S.D	Number	D.F	T value	sig
The role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism	Male	3.33	0.90	70	118	.617	.539
	Female	3.23	0.79	50			

The results of Table (4) show that there are no statistically significant differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism due to gender, as the statistic value (T) reached (0.617), which is a non-statistically significant value at the level of significance (0.05) or less, and this indicates and confirms an agreement in The viewpoints between male and female journalists that Jordanian television is fighting terrorism at a close level and a medium-level degree, and these results are consistent to some extent with the results of the study (Mansour, 2007) which confirmed that there are no statistical differences in the evaluation of Jordanian television coverage of terrorism issues due to the gender variable, as well. These results are in agreement to a certain extent with the study (Al-Tahat, 2016), which showed that all members of the study sample have similar level perceptions regarding the degree of Al-Rai newspaper's contribution to combating terrorism by gender.

Results of the fourth question:

Text of the question: Are there statistically significant differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism that can be attributed to the job?

The Independent Sample T-test was used to identify the differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism attributed to the job variable, and Table (5) illustrates that:

Table (5)
Independent Sample T-test to identify the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism is attributable to the job

Source	Total Gender	Mean	S.D	Number	D.F	T value	sig
The role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism	Male	3.32	0.79	63	118	.477	.634
	Female	3.25	0.92	57			

The results of Table (5) show that there are no statistically significant differences in the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism attributable to the job, as the statistic value (T) reached (0.477), which is a non-statistically significant value at the level of significance (0.05) or less, and this indicates and confirms an agreement in The viewpoints among journalists, regardless of their job, whether they are editors or delegates, that Jordanian television is fighting terrorism at a similar level and to a medium level.

Recommendations:

Based on the results of the theoretical and field study, the researcher submits a set of proposals that may contribute to increasing the role of Jordanian television in combating terrorism, represented in the following:

First: Increasing the number of local, Arab and international news and reports broadcast by Jordanian television to educate society about the dangers of the phenomenon of terrorism.

Second: Increasing the number of media programs that explain and analyze the motives of terrorism and its future plans that pose the real threat to the Arab world and the world.

Third: Broadcast media reports focusing on the meaning of the Arab peoples as a result of the work of terrorist organizations that have come to threaten the unity of some Arab countries.

Fourth: Disseminating information materials that include the size of the economic, social and scientific losses caused by terrorist organizations that carry out their terrorist activities in the Arab countries.

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